

Simultaneous Estimation of Catechin, Rutin, Quercetin in *Mangifera Indica* Linn by RP-HPLC

Madhuri Kadam, Dipak Raut, M. J. Chavhan

Amruthvahini College Of Pharmacy, Sangamner, Dist-Ahilyanagar, 422605.

ABSTRACT

There has been a resurgence in usage of herbal medicine past few decades, not only among traditional medicine users (ethano-medicine) but also among the modern consumers. The global herbal market size was estimated to be US\$83 billion in 2019 and it is expected to reach (1)US\$550 billion by 2030 at a CARGR 18.9% through 2030. So it becomes important to analysis the herbal medicaments.

Keywords: Catechin, Rutin, Quercetin, RP-HPLC.

INTRODUCTION

Mangifera Indica Plant:

Mangifera indica L. or mango is one of the common species of the genus *Mangifera* (family Anacardiaceae)[2]. It is a medium-to-large evergreen tree with various parts (roots, barks, leaves, ripe and unripe pulps, seeds, and flowers) that have long been used in ethnomedicines [2]. Nowadays, in the situation where the consumers are actively searching for health promoting alternatives for traditional crops, mango is one of the tropical fruits that has been in high demands[2]. The pharmaceutical activities of mango are tremendously diverse, which is considered to derive from the bioactive compounds present in different mango plant parts, including protines, vitamin A, vitamin C, carotenoids, phenolic compounds(mangiferin, catechines, rutin, quercetin, gallotannins, and iriflophenones), gallic acid, benzoic acid, fibers, carbohydrates, and minerals [2]. The phytochemical profile of mango, and consequently its biological effects.

There are no sources in the current document., can be greatly varied according to the variety, maturity stages and cultivations areas.

Phytochemistry:

According to the IUPAC nomenclature, catechin is identified as: (2R,3S)-2-(3,4- Dihydroxyphenyl)-3,4-dihydro-2H- chromene-3,5,7-triol. a pigment mangiferin- was first isolated from mangoes (*Mangifera indica*, Anacardiaceae). Catechin are a type of flavan-3- ol, consisting of flavon skeleton with a hydroxyl group at the 3- position.

According to the IUPAC nomenclature, Rutin: 3,3',4',5,7- Pentahydroxyflavone-3- rutinoide. Rutin is a flavonoid glycoside, consisting of quercetin linked to a rutinose sugar moiety. Rutin is present in the leaves, stem, and fruits of the mango plant. Rutin is synthesized through the flavonoids biosynthetic pathway, which involves the conversion of phenylalanine to flavonoids.

Quercetin IUPAC nomenclature is 2-(3,4-Dihydroxy phenyl)-3,5,7- trihydroxy-4H- chromen-4-one. Quercetin is a flavonoide aglycon, consisting of a flavan skeleton with hydroxyl group at the 3,5, and 7- positions.

Uses:

Whole herb of *mangifera indica* (Anacardiaceae), has been used as a to treat Immunomodulatory, anti-HIV, antiviral, anti- inflammation, cardioprotective, antipyretic activity, anticancer, antidiabetic, radioprotection, neuroprotective, antimicrobial,

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

hepatoprotective, hypo Cholesterol activity and antioxidant activity.

Antioxidant Activity:

Mango it has been shown that antioxidant play an important role in preventing oxidative stress related diseases and aging. Numerous data on the antioxidant activity of various plant material have been reported. the ethanolic extract of mango leaves exhibited antioxidant effects through 1,1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) radical scavenging and superoxide dismutase (SOD)-like activities with half maximal inhibitory concentration (IC₅₀) values of 14.94 and 68.0 mg/ml, respectively. If the antioxidant activity of oldmango leaves extract is confirmed, the utility of pruned old dark green leaves for the preparing cosmetic and/or supplemental ingredient with health –enhancing properties may be increased. Since mango is an evergreen plant, leaves at different three stages of growth, young dark reddish brown leaves, young yellow leaves and pruned old dark green leaves, were collectable during pruning at the same time in late summer. This prompted us to examine the relationship between the maturation of leaves and this antioxidant activity.

Extraction:

Extraction is the first step to separate the desired natural products from the raw material. Extraction methods include solvent extraction, distillation method, pressing and sublimation, according to the extraction principle. Solvent extraction is the most widely used method.

PLANT PROFILE

Botanical Name: *Mangifera Indica*.

Description: It is a large green tree, valued mainly for its fruits, both green and ripe.

Belonging to Family: Anacardiaceous.

Morphological Characters: It is a bushy or herbaceous plant growing up to 15-30m tall. Its stem are rough in texture and its leaves are simple, shiny and dark green.

Geographical Source: *Mangifera Indica* is widely cultivated of tropical world. The mango tree is considered indigenously to southern Asia, especially Myanmar and Asam state of India.

Uses: Antibacterial, Antioxidant, Anti-inflammatory, Anticancer, diuretic, Antipyretic.

Taxonomical Classification

Taxonomical classification of *Mangifera Indica*

Type of system for classification	Name of the system
Division	Magnoliophyta-Flowering plants
Sub-division	Tracheobionta
Class	Dicotyledons
Order	Sapindales
Sub-order	Sapindales
Family	Anacardiaceae
Genera	<i>Mangifera</i>
Species	<i>M.indica</i>

Image of whole plant of *Mangifera Indica*.

Chemical Constituents

The plant contains saponins, alkaloids, Flavonoid, tannins, phenols, Volatile oil, resins, terpenoids, proteins and glycosides.

Chemical structure of chemical marker compounds presents in *Mangifera*.

MATERIAL AND EQUIPMENTS

Herbal Drug:

Herbal Drug and supplier.

Sr.No	Herbal Drug	Supplier
1.	Mango leaves	Sangamner (LocalMarket)

Standard Drug:**Standard Drug and supplier.**

Sr. No	Name of Drug	Company Name	Brand Name	CAS-NO	Mol. Weight	Appearance
1	Catechin	Yucca Enterprises	Yucca	88191-48-4	308.28 g/mol	Powder
2	Rutin	Research Lab Fine Chemical Industry's	Research Lab	250249-75-3	664.56 g/mol	Powder
3	Quercetin	Loba Chemie PVT.LTD.	Loba chemie	849061-97-8	302.24 g/mol	Powder

Chemical used

Sr.no.	Chemical name	Grade	Purchased from
1.	Acetonitrile(ACN)	HPLC grade	Merck life Science
2.	Sodium dihydrogen orthophosphate	HPLC grade	Otto ChemiePvt. Ltd.
3.	Methanol	HPLC grade	Merck life science
4.	Sodium Lauryl Sulphate	HPLC grade	Otto ChemiePvt. Ltd.
5.	Ethyl acetate	AR grade	Loba ChemiePvt. Ltd.
6.	Dichloromethane	AR grade	Loba ChemiePvt. Ltd.
7.	Toluene	AR grade	Loba Chemie Pvt. Ltd.
8.	DPPH	AR grade	Tokyo chemical industrial co,Ltd.

Instruments used:**Lists of apparatus/instruments used**

Sr.no.	Name of Instruments	Company	Model
1.	Digital Balance	SHIMADZU	AP225 WD
2.	Sonicator	PCI Analytical	D-120/LH
3.	HPLC	Agilent technology	1260Infinity-IIIDAD-1260
4.	IR	BRUKEROPTICS	ALPHAT
5.	MILLI-Q-WATER System	MERK MILLIPORE	Direct-Q3
6.	Digital pH meter	SYSTRONICS	MKVI
7.	UV Spectroscopy	SHIMADZU	UV-1900I

EXPERIMENTAL WORK**Collection of plant material:**

Mango leaves (*Mangifera indica* L) collected from the medicinal garden of Amrutvahini College of

Pharmacy, Sangamner. Leaves were washed with tap water and shade dried (at room temperature for 4-5 days) and grinded to get powder. The powder of the drug was stored at the room temperature. The standard Catechin >95% were purchased from Yucca

Enterprises and Standard Rutin >95% were purchased from Research lab (Mumbai). Standard Quercetin > 95% were purchased from Loba Chemie PVT. LTD(Mumbai)

Sample Preparation:

Grind the dried green mango leaves into a coarse powder using a grinder and pass through an 120- mesh sives. This increases the surface area for the extraction process.

Mango leaves powder

Extraction of Phytochemical investigation:

Successive extraction process:

Successive extraction is the process used to extract specific compounds or groups of compounds from a sample using multiple solvents with varying polarities. Successive extraction of dried green mango leaves typically involves using solvents to progressively extract different compounds from mango leaves. This process can be divided into several stages, each using a different solvent or combination of solvents to target specific components.

Solvent selection:

Prepare different solvent for successive extractions, starting with less polar solvent and moving to more polar solvent (e.g., petroleum ether, chloroform, ethyl acetate, methanol, ethanol, and water).

Extraction of mango leaves:

Soxhlet extraction is most preferred for herbal active constitution isolation. 200 gm dried mango leaves powder was used for extraction. Powder was passed through 85 mesh sieves to remove fine and coarse particles. Then powder was used for extraction by using Soxhlet extraction

First Extraction: (Dichloromethane)

200 gm of dried mango leaves powder was taken in Soxhlet apparatus with sufficient amount of solvent such as Dichloromethane. And extraction was carried out for seven days. After completion of extraction, Dichloromethane extract (free from leaves powder) collected at the end. The residue (leaves powder free from solvent) was used in second extraction.

Second Extraction:(Ethyl Acetate)

Use the residue from the first extraction and add the ethyl acetate to the residue and repeat the extraction process in seven days. The point of extraction is determined by reaction with iodine vapours. A small spot is applied on TLC plate by using capillary tube and placed it iodine chamber, if colourless spot is observed that indicates completion of extraction.

Identification of compounds by Thin Layer Chromatography:

The redeemed percoated aluminium thin layer chromatography plates are used for identification of compounds in extract and isolated compounds from column chromatography. Application of sample was done by sealed capillary tube on TLC plate at a point about 1 cm from bottom. Spot was aired dried. Chamber saturation was done by pouring mobile phase into chamber an capped it with lead and allowed to saturate for 30 min. After saturation of chamber then spot of samples was given on plate, it was kept in chamber. The solvent level in bottom of chamber must not be above as spotted material, may dissolve in pool of vent instead of undergoing chromatography. Then solvent was allowed to run for 5-10 min on silica plate. Visualization was done by suitable visualizing agent, Aluminium chloride spraying reagent and ammonium vapors are used, and then R_f value was calculated by following formula,

Rf=Distance traveled by solute/Distance travelled by solvent

UV Spectrophotometric Analysis

Determination of wavelength of maximum absorbance (λ_{max}) of Standard drug

1. Preparation of standard stock solution

Stock solution of drug (1mg/ml) is prepared by dissolving 100mg of drug in 100ml solvent methanol (to get 1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ drug solution) with vigorous shaking and further sonicated for about 10 minutes. 10 ml of this stock solution is diluted to 100 ml of methanol to get this solution containing 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of drug. Wavelength of maximum absorption was determined by scanning 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ solution of std drugs using UV spectrophotometer from 200-400 nm. This std drugs showed maximum absorbance at Rutin 257 nm, Quercetin 370 nm, Catechin 280 nm.

2. Preparation of solution for calibration curve of standard drugs.

Stock solution of drug (1 mg/ml) is prepared by dissolving 100 mg of drug in 100 ml of solvent methanol (to get 1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ drug solution) with vigorous shaking and further sonicated for about 10 minutes. 10 ml of this stock solution is diluted to 100 ml of methanol to get this solution containing 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of drug. Take the respective samples (0.2 ml, 0.4ml, 0.6ml, 0.8 ml, 1ml) in each 10 ml volumetric flask and makeup the volume upto 10 ml methanol. The absorbances of this solutions were measured at particular wave length of std drugs (Rutin257nm, Quercetin370nm, Catechin280nm) against a blank methanol. The calibration curve was obtained by plotting the absorbance of standard drugs versus the concentration of standard drugs.

RP-HPLC Method:

The chromatography system used to perform development of this method consist Agilent 1260 infinity II RP-HPLC equipped with quaternary pump. Sample injected with a 20 μl loop, DAD detector and Agilent C18(250 mm \times 4.6 mm, 5 μm) column. The

HPLC system was equipped with open lab software for acquisition and quantification of peaks.

Preparation of Standard Solution:

Stock solution of standard drug was prepared by transferring accurately weight 250 mg Catechin, 50 mg Rutin and 10 mg Quercetin into a 100 ml clean and dry volumetric flask and add 20 ml of Acetonitrile sonicate for 10 min and volume makeup with Acetonitrile. Then Remove the 5ml solution and make the volume in 50 ml acetonitrile.

Preparation of Ethyl Acetate Extract Solution.

Stock solution of Ethyl Acetate Extract (1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) was prepared by transferring accurately weighed, 10 mg extract into a 10ml volumetric flask and adding 5 ml Acetonitrile. The mixture was sonicated for 10 min to dissolve the content and the solution was then diluted to volume with the same solvent mixture. Standard solution Ethel Acetate extract was prepared.

Preparation of optimized method

0.05M Sodium Dihydrogen Ortho Phosphate Buffer (NaH_2PO_4): To prepare 1L of 0.05M Sodium Dihydrogen Orthophosphate Buffer, dissolve 7.80 gm of Sodium dihydrogen phosphate dihydrate ($\text{NaH}_2\text{PO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) in distilled water, Adjust the pH if needed, and make up to 1 liter.

0.1% Sodium Lauryl Sulphate (SLS): Weight 0.1gm of SLS and add 80 ml of distilled water in beaker, stir continuously SLS is completely dissolved. Transfer the solution in 100 ml of volumetric flask and make up the volume to 100ml with distilled water. Mix well.

Acetonitrile gradient: Acetonitrile gradient was taken in clean mobile phase bottle sonicated for degassing and attached to HPLC port.

Trial No.1

In trial changes are made of chromatographic condition such as mobile phase ratio as from vendor Method.

Chromatographic condition of trial 1

Parameter	Conditions
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Column	Phenomenex4.5x 250mm5 μ C18silica.
Mobile phase	Water: Acetonitrile (70:30v/v)
Flowrate	1 ml /min
Run time	30 Min
Column Temperature	30 ⁰ c
Injection Volume	20 μ l
Detection wave length	272nm.
Diluent	Acetonitrile

Trial No. 2**Chromatographic condition of trial 2**

Parameter	Conditions
Column	Phenomenex4.5x 250mm5 μ C18silica.
Mobile phase	0.01MPotassium Dihydrogen Orthophosphate: ACN(70:30v/v)
Flowrate	1ml/min
Run time	20 Min
Column Temperature	30 ⁰ c
Injection Volume	20 μ l
Detection wavelength	272nm
Diluent	Acetonitrile

Trial no. 3**Chromatographic condition of trial 3**

Parameter	Conditions
Column	Phenomenex4.5x 250mm5 μ C18silica.
Mobile phase	0.01MPotassium Dihydrogen Orthophosphate: ACN(50:50v/v)
Flowrate	1ml/min
Run time	20 Min
Column Temperature	30 ⁰ c
Injection Volume	20 μ l
Detection wavelength	272nm
Diluent	Acetonitrile

Trial No. 4**Chromatographic condition of trial 4**

Parameter	Conditions
Column	Phenomenex4.5x250mm5 μ C18silica.
Mobile phase	0.05M sodium dihydrogen orthophosphate Buffer and0.1% sodiumlauryl sulphate: Acetonitrile(70:30v/v)
Flowrate	1 ml/min
Run time	20 Min
Column Temperature	30 ⁰ c
Injection Volume	20 μ l.
Detection wave length	272nm
Diluent	Acetonitrile

Trial No. 5

Chromatographic condition of trial 5

Parameter	Conditions
Column	Phenomenex4.5x250mm5 μ C18silica.
Mobile phase	0.05M sodium dihydrogen orthophosphate Buffer and 0.1%sodiumlauryl sulphate: Acetonitrile(65:35v/v)
Flowrate	1 ml/min
Run time	10 Min
Column Temperature	30 ⁰ c
Injection Volume	20 μ l
Detection wavelength	272nm
Diluent	Acetonitrile

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Mangifera Indica extract

Which appears as a coarse, reddish-brown powder after solvent evaporations. The color and texture of the extract indicates the presence of polyphenolic compounds such as flavonoids, tannins, and phenolic acids, which are commonly reported in mango plant parts.[7]

Identification of Standard drug

Organoleptic properties of drug

Organoleptic properties of standard drug

Image of ethyl acetate extract of *Mangifera Indica*.

Sr.No.	Organoleptic property	Catechin	Rutin Ruu	Quercetin
1.	Colour	Brown	Yellowish-Green	Yellow powder
2.	Odour	Slightly astringent	Characteristic odour	Characteristic odour
3	Solubility	Water, Ethanol, Methanol	Ethanol, Methanol, Springly Soluble in Water	Ethanol, Methanol, Springly Soluble in Water

Result of phytochemical analysis of flavonoids and polyphenols

Phytochemical Analysis of flavonoid and Polyphenols.

Sr.No.	Test	Remark	Inference
1.	Test for flavonoid Shinoda test	Yellow colour observed	Flavonoid are present
2.	Test for Polyphenols 0.5%FeCl ₃	Deep Blue-black colour observed	Polyphenols are present.

TLC (Thin Layer Chromatography)**TLC of the Ethyl Acetate extract.****TLC of the Ethyl acetate (Mangifera Indica) extract**

The extract of Mangifera Indica the solvent system is Toluene: Ethyl Acetate: Formic Acid (5: 4:1)1. Extract 2. Rutin ($R_f=0.47$) 3. Catechin ($R_f= 0.25$) 4. Quercetin ($R_f=0.5$)[33]

TLC of Different Fractions for Mangifera indica extract.**TLC of different fraction for Mangifera Indica Extract**

The different fractions of Mangifera indica extract in solvent system is Toluene: Ethyl acetate: Formic acid (5:4:1) 1). Fraction No 11. 2) Fraction No 12. 3) Fraction No 13. 4) Std Quercetin 5) Std Catechin Fractions was compared in Standard.[33]

FTIR Spectrum of Rutin

Sr. No.	Functional group	Standard Range(cm^{-1})	Observe Range(cm^{-1})	Structure of Rutin
1	O-H Strech	3800-3600	3745.25	
2	C-H Strech	3200-3000	3183.27	
3	C-H Strech	3000-2800	2915.56	
4	C=O Strech	1800-1600	1652.54	
5	C=C Strech	1600-1500	1596.35	
6	C-H Bending	1500-1400	1454.83	
7	C-O Strech	1300-1200	1291.09	
8	C-O Strech	1200-1000	1129.28	
9	C-O Strech	1200-1000	1006.36	
10	C-H Bending	900-700	801.42	

Interpretation of FTIR of Catechin

Sr. No	Functional group	Standard Range(cm^{-1})	Observed Range (cm^{-1})	Structure of Catechin
1	O-H Stretching	3400-3200	3420.36	
2	C-H Stretching	3200-3000	3165.15	
3	C=O Stretching	1800-1600	1615.20	
4	C=C Stretching	1600-1500	1517.39	
5	C-H Bending	1500-1400	1465.14	
6	C-O Stretching	1300-1200	1357.60	
7	C-O Stretching	1200-1000	1190.34	
8	C-H Bending	1000-900	966.41	
9	C-H Bending	900-700	857.60	

Interpretation of FTIR of Quercetin[35]

Sr No	Functional group	Standard Range(cm^{-1})	Observed Range (cm^{-1})	Structure of Quercetin
1	C-H Stretching	3200-3000	3122.60	
2	C-H Stretching	3000-2800	2886.17	
3	C=O Stretching	1800-1600	1616.63	
4	C=C Stretching	1600-1500	1518.98	
5	C-H Bending	1500-1400	1458.70	
6	C-O Stretching	1300-1200	1258.32	
7	C-O Stretching	1200-1000	1171.41	
8	C-H Bending	1000-900	966.97	
9	C-H Bending	900-700	810.54	

FTIR Spectrum of *Mangifera Indica* Extract:

IR Spectrum of Ethylacetate extract

Determination of Wavelength(λ_{max})

Determination of Wavelength of maximum absorbance(λ_{max}) of Rutin

UV spectrum of standard Rutin

Wavelength of maximum absorption was determined by scanning 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ solution of Rutin using UV spectrophotometer from 200-400 nm. This showed maximum absorbance at 257 nm.

Determination of Wavelength of maximum absorbance(λ_{max}) of Quercetin

UV spectrum of standard Quercetin.

Wavelength of maximum absorption was determined by scanning 100 µg/ml solution of Quercetin using UV spectrophotometer from 200-400 nm. This showed maximum absorbance at 370 nm.[35]

Determination of Wavelength of maximum absorbance(λ_{max}) of Catechin

UV spectrum of standard Catechin

Wavelength of maximum absorption was determined by scanning 100 µg/ml solution of Catechin using UV spectrophotometer from 200-400 nm. This showed maximum absorbance at 280nm.

Determination of Wavelength of maximum absorbance(λ_{max}) of ethylacetate extract:

UV spectrum of Mangifera indica Extract.

Wavelength of maximum absorption was determined by scanning 100 µg/ml solution of Extract using UV spectrophotometer from 200-400 nm.

The antioxidant activity of standard flavonoids (Rutin, Quercetin, and Catechin) and the ethyl acetate extract of Mangifera indica leaves was evaluated using the DPPH(2,2- diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl) radical scavenging methods. The % inhibition of DPPH radical was calculated at various concentration (10-40 ppm), and IC50 values were determined.

Antioxidant Activity:

Comparative Antioxidant Activity of Standard and Sample Extracts using DPPH Assay:

Sr.No	Sample	Concentration (ppm)	Absorbance \pm SD	%Inhibition	IC50 (μ g/ml)
1	DPPH	-	0.366	-	-
2	Rutin	10	0.250 \pm 0.0075	31.602	29.840
3	Rutin	20	0.191 \pm 0.0140	47.723	
4	Rutin	30	0.149 \pm 0.0068	59.198	
5	Rutin	40	0.109 \pm 0.0024	70.036	
6	Quercetin	10	0.243 \pm 0.0102	33.424	

7	Quercetin	20	0.184 ± 0.0008	49.726	35.854
8	Quercetin	30	0.105 ± 0.0042	71.311	
9	Quercetin	40	0.043 ± 0.0106	88.069	
10	Catechin	10	0.293 ± 0.0024	19.854	42.205
11	Catechin	20	0.247 ± 0.0222	32.422	
12	Catechin	30	0.207 ± 0.0216	43.442	
13	Catechin	40	0.159 ± 0.0089	56.466	12.992
14	Extract	10	0.201 ± 0.0066	44.990	
15	Extract	20	0.162 ± 0.0028	55.646	
16	Extract	30	0.127 ± 0.0014	65.300	
17	Extract	40	0.105 ± 0.0023	71.220	

Observation table for Antioxidant activity by DPPH Assay.

Mangifera indica extract exhibited the strongest antioxidant activity with the lowest

IC₅₀(12.992μg/ml), followed by Rutin, Quercetin, and Catechin. This suggests that the ethyl acetate extract of Mangifera Indica leaves is rich in antioxidant phytochemicals and may be a promising natural antioxidant source.

Calibration Curve of Rutinin DPPH Assay:

Calibration curve of Rutin in DPPH Assay.

This graph represents the DPPH radical scavenging activity (antioxidant activity) of Rutin at different concentrations. It plots the % inhibition on the Y-axis

against concentration(ppm)on the X-axis. The R² values = 0.9904, which indicates a very high correlation and strong linearity, these confirm that Rutin shows a dose dependent antioxidant activity.[42]

Calibration curve of Quercetin in DPPH Assay.

This graph represents the DPPH radical scavenging activity of Quercetin at increasing concentrations. The Y-axis shows the % inhibition, while the X-axis shows concentration in ppm. The linear equation and high $R^2(0.997)$ value demonstrate a strong

correlation, suggesting that Quercetin exhibits a concentration dependent antioxidant effects.

Comparative DPPH Radical Scavenging Activity of Standard Antioxidants and Ethyl Acetate Extract:

As observe in fig all samples exhibits a dose dependent increase in % inhibition. Among the standards, Quercetin showed the highest antioxidant activity, followed by rutin, then Catechin. The ethyl acetate extract also demonstrated antioxidant potential, although it was lower compared to the pure

compounds. This comparative analysis validates the relevance of *Mangifera indica* extract as a potential natural antioxidant source, although less potent than the pure standards.[2]

Calibration curve of Markers and Ethyl acetate extract by UV Spectrophotometry

Sr.No	Sample	Concentration	ABS Mean	Equation	R^2
1	Rutin	2	0.008667	Y=0.0472x-0.0903	$R^2=0.9959$
2		4	0.027667		
3		6	0.046667		
4		8	0.067667		
5		10	0.087333		
6	Quercetin	2	0.0031	Y=0.0251x-0.035	$R^2=0.9971$
7		4	0.090333		
8		6	0.203		
9		8	0.297333		
10		10	0.372		
11	Catechin	2	0.011667		
12		4	0.065		
13		6	0.121333		
14		8	0.167333		
15		10	0.211		
16	Extract	2	0.021333		
17		4	0.055333		

18		6	0.101667
19		8	0.146667
20		10	0.208

Calibration curve of markers and ethylacetate extract by UV spectrophotometry.

This table presents UV spectrophotometric calibration data for the simultaneous estimation of three flavonoids Rutin, Quercetin, Catechin as well as their presence in ethyl acetate extract.

CONCLUSION

A significant amount of Rutin, Quercetin, and Catechin was detected in the extract of *Mangifera Indica*. It is reported that flavonoid has good pharmacological, antioxidant and nutraceutical activities. Antioxidant properties of flavonoids are well known to be responsible for human health benefits. The above study has shown that *Mangifera Indica* shows different chemical constituents (e.g. Mangiferin, Rutin, Quercetin, Catechin, Gallic Acid, Kaempferol etc). In the present research work, a successfully attempt was made for development and validation of HPLC-DAD method for simultaneous estimation of Rutin, Quercetin, Catechin. The proposed HPLC method is simple, rapid, specific, accurate and precise for determination of the flavonoid Rutin, Quercetin, Catechin. The method was validated and satisfactory result were obtained for some of the characteristics tested. The system suitability parameter were selected for HPLC method and data has shown good peak intensity, good retention time of the drug that define the suitability method. Because of the short chromatographic run time (10), the developed method can be adopted for the routine quantification and quality control of Rutin, Quercetin.

REFERENCES

- Naveen, P., Lingaraju, H. B., & Prasad, K. S. (2017). Rapid Development and Validation of Improved Reversed-Phase High-performance Liquid Chromatography Method for the Quantification of Mangiferin, a Polyphenol Xanthone Glycoside in *Mangifera Indica*. *Pharmacognosy research*, 9(2), 215–219. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0974-8490.204652>
- Nguyen Thi Truc Loan, Dang Thanh Long, Pham Nguyen Dong Yen, Truong Thi Minh Hanh, Tri Nhut Pham, Dung Thuy Nguyen Pham Purification Process of Mangiferin from *Mangifera indica* L. Leaves and Evaluation of Its Bioactivities by Processes 2021, 9(5), 852; <https://doi.org/10.3390/pr9050852>
- Yuanguang Zu, Chunying Li, Yujie Fu, Chunjian Zhao Simultaneous determination of catechin, rutin, quercetin kaempferol and isorhamnetin in the extract of sea buckthorn (*Hippophae rhamnoides* L.) leaves by RP-HPLC with DAD July 2006 *Journal of Pharmaceutical and Biomedical Analysis* 41(3):714-9 DOI:10.1016/j.jpba.2005.04.052
- Kumar, V., & Chandra, S. (2015). LC-ESI/MS determination of xanthone and secoiridoid glycosides from in vitro regenerated and in vivo *Swertia chirayita*. *Physiology and molecular biology of plants: an international journal of functional plant biology*, 21 Jyotshna, Srivastava, P., Killadi, B., & Shanker, K. (2015).
- Uni-dimensional double development HPTLC-densitometry method for simultaneous analysis of mangiferin and lupeol content in mango (*Mangifera indica*) pulp and peel during storage. *Food chemistry*, 176, 91–98. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2014.12.034>(1), 51–60.
- El-Nashar, H. A. S., El-Labbad, E. M., Al-Azzawi, M. A., & Ashmawy, N. S. (2022). A New Xanthone Glycoside from *Mangifera indica* L.: Physicochemical Properties and In Vitro Anti-Skin Aging Activities. *Molecules (Basel, Switzerland)*, 27(9), 2609. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules27092609>
- Shah, K. A., Patel, M. B., Patel, R. J., & Parmar, P. K. (2010). *Mangifera indica* (mango). *Pharmacognosy reviews*, 4(7), 42–48. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0973-7847.65325>
- Kumar, M., Saurabh, V., Tomar, M., Hasan, M., Changan, S., Sasi, M., Maheshwari, C., Prajapati, U., Singh, S., Prajapat, R. K., Dhupal, S., Punia, S., Amarowicz, R., & Mekhemar, M. (2021). Mango (*Mangifera indica* L.) Leaves: Nutritional Composition, Phytochemical Profile, and Health-Promoting Bioactivities. *Antioxidants (Basel, Switzerland)*, 10(2), 299. <https://doi.org/10.3390/antiox10020299>

9. Reddeman, R. A., Glávits, R., Endres, J. R., Clewell, A. E., Hirka, G., Vértesi, A., Béres, E., & Szakonyiné, I. P. (2019). A Toxicological Evaluation of Mango Leaf Extract (*Mangifera indica*) Containing 60% Mangiferin. *Journal of toxicology*, 2019, 4763015. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/4763015>
10. Qiu, X., Zhao, J. L., Hao, C., Yuan, C., Tian, N., Xu, Z. S., & Zou, R. M. (2016). Simultaneous determination of mangiferin and neomangiferin in rat plasma by UPLC-MS/MS and its application for pharmacokinetic study. *Journal of pharmaceutical and biomedical analysis*, 124, 138–142. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpba.2016.02.034>
11. Molecular formula and molecular weight of mangiferin. (Source: http://www.made-in-china.com/showroom/byro_2000/product-list/Sap-Extract-1.html)
12. Clasificación of *Mangifera indica*. (Source: <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Mangifera>) Parts used for the estimation of mangiferin in *Mangifera indica*. (Source: <http://www.raintree.com/mango.htm>)
13. Ivan Ross A, *Medicinal plants of the world* Published by Humana Press Totowa, New Jersey, 197.
14. Rastogi RP, Mehrota BN, *Compendium of Indian Medicinal Plants*, Central Drug Research Institute Lucknow; India, 265-6(1991).
15. Rastogi RP, Mehrota BN, *Compendium of Indian Medicinal Plants*, Central Drug Research Institute Lucknow; India, 407-9(1993).
16. Rastogi RP, Mehrota BN, *Compendium of Indian Medicinal Plants*, Central Drug Research Institute Lucknow; India, 456(1995).
17. Rastogi RP, Mehrota BN *Compendium of Indian Medicinal Plants*, Central Drug Research Institute Lucknow; India, 524(1998).
18. Naveen, P., Lingaraju, H. B., & Prasad, K. S. (2017). Rapid Development and Validation of Improved Reversed-Phase High-performance Liquid Chromatography Method for the Quantification of Mangiferin in a Polyphenol Xanthone Glycoside in *Mangifera Indica*. *Pharmacognosy research*, 9(2), 215–219. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0974-8490.204652>.

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